

Meeting Report

Observational Medical Outcome Partnership (OMOP) Special Interest Group: Fourth Meeting

Introduction

The Health Data Research Alliance held its 4th OMOP Special Interest Group meeting via MS teams on Friday, the **28th of June 2024, from 14:30 to 16:00 (UK time)**. Co-chair Prof. Geoff Hall welcomed the participants and thanked everyone for making time to attend the 4th OMOP SIG meeting. He noted that the meeting agenda had been shared in advance, and Geoff introduced himself as a medical oncologist in Leeds, and the Chief Clinical Data Officer for HDR UK.

Real World Evidence Network: Introduction (Geoff Hall)

[\[Presentation Slides\]](#)

Geoff Hall introduced the Real-World Evidence Network, established by HDRUK. He explained that in April, HDRUK announced a funding call to establish a coordination centre for the network, which would leverage data from multiple UK sources. The goal is to use the OMOP common data model to enhance the efficiency of multicentre and multinational research studies. This initiative aligns with HDRUK's mission of accelerating healthcare data use for discoveries. The funding comprised two parts: establishing the Coordination Centre and recruiting OMOP-ready data partners. An open call for applications resulted in several submissions. Geoff expressed his pleasure in announcing that HDRUK supported the coordinating centre bid from **Dani Prieto-Alhambra, Ed Burn, and Marti Catala Sabate** from University of Oxford.

Presentations

Real World Evidence Network (RWE) (Dani Prieto-Alhambra)

This presentation gives an insight and plans of the RWE.

- The team has extensive experience in international projects, including mapping data to OMOP and creating analytical tools through the DARWIN-EU initiative.
- The multidisciplinary team covers the entire pipeline from data mapping to evidence generation, emphasizing collaboration and capacity building. Their mission is to improve human health using real-world data, with a focus on training, capacity enhancement, data quality, and analytical methods. We plan to establish a pilot network of seven data partners across the UK, selected through an open call.
- Pilot studies, co-designed with various stakeholders and citizens, will test the network's capabilities and generate actionable data.
- Training will be integrated to enhance capacity, addressing the challenges of applying international analytical tools in the UK.
- The work is divided into three packages: onboarding data partners, executing pilot studies, and ensuring sustainability. Selection criteria for data partners include research readiness, governance, technical infrastructure, database richness, and geographical coverage, with extra points for unique data domains.
- Pilot studies will prioritize impact, inclusivity, alignment with HDRUK's programs, collaboration, novelty, and feasibility.

During the meeting, congratulations were extended to the team on their appointment as the coordinating network, with anticipation of successful collaboration. The importance of delivering working exemplars to convince the broader NHS to adopt the initiative was emphasised.

The discussion also covered federated analysis of data. It was noted that international federated analysis typically runs common code on local data sets and then meta-analyses the results, whereas “true” federation involves an analytic server accessing data directly. Governance challenges were cited as reasons for the current approach, which involves running analyses separately in each data set and compiling the results.

Further discussion on “true” federation, including ongoing work in Europe using the Vantage 6 platform, was suggested.

The Use of OMOP for research in paediatrics, a clinical academic perspective (Ofran Almassawi - Great Ormond Street Hospital)
[\[Presentation Link\]](#)

The presentation highlighted the current state and potential of paediatric research, focusing on data utilisation and the challenges faced in paediatric studies. The speaker outlined the role of the Children's Medicines Research and Innovation Centre at Great Ormond Street Hospital (GOSH) and provided insights into the hospital's patient demographics and research infrastructure.

- GOSH, in partnership with University College London's Institute of Child Health, is the largest paediatric Biomedical Research Centre (BRC) in the UK, handling around 300 patient encounters annually across 66 specialties. The hospital's Digital Research Innovation and Virtual Environment (DRIVE) unit processes electronic health system data, making it pseudonymized and research-ready with pre-approved ethics.
- OMOP is important in paediatric research due to the unique patient population and the challenges of clinical trials in children. Clinical trials in paediatrics are resource-intensive and yield small numbers, highlighting the need for alternative data sources like Real World Data (RWD).
- RWD in paediatrics is crucial due to the high use of off-label and unlicensed drugs, with only 14% of medicines licensed for children upon market entry. RWD is necessary to achieve high-quality evidence, given that children's adverse reactions to medicines are three times higher than in adults.
- New methodologies like causal machine learning are attractive for research in paediatrics, and the important of characterising studies in paediatrics. It is important for an organized effort to develop a paediatric-specific OMOP initiative to leverage large-scale, linked electronic health records and improve drug utilization and disease characterization studies.
- There is currently limited focus on paediatrics within OHDSI. During the first UK OHDSI Studyathon on large-scale drug utilization (specifically fluoroquinolones), it became clear that paediatric and adult data had to be analysed separately due to differences in treatment, treatment effects, dosage, and unlicensed use. This highlighted the importance of having a dedicated paediatric OMOP representation. A good starting point would be forming a group with hospitals that have a significant paediatric population.

- The idea of creating a specific OMOP for paediatrics which would allow for focused data mapping for paediatric studies rather than mapping the entire hospital's data, making the task more manageable. With the abundance of electronic health record data, there is a strong motivation and urgent need to develop high-quality evidence for medicine use in children.

Discussion

- Several participants discussed the balance between electronic health records (EHR) and OMOP, emphasizing the need for standardization. The idea of a paediatric-specific OMOP model was debated, with concerns about maintaining standardization while addressing paediatric-specific needs. One participant highlighted previous efforts to create a paediatric network within EHDPEN and suggested revisiting these initiatives.
- Participants expressed support for the proposed paediatric research initiatives and emphasized the importance of nationwide and international collaboration to achieve significant patient numbers for studies. The potential for study-specific OMOP conversions was discussed as a practical approach to engage hospitals in collaborative research without overwhelming them with extensive data conversion tasks. A participant shared their experience with OMOP conversions, including paediatric data, and supported starting with small, broad studies to build a foundation for more complex research.

How RWE is transforming regulatory Body decision making (Alex Pacurariu- European Medicine Agency)

[\[Presentation Slides\]](#)

This presentation focused on how real-world evidence (RWE) is transforming regulatory decision-making. An overview of the necessity and current applications of RWE in regulatory contexts was provided.

- To show the novelty of Real-World Evidence (RWE), several studies were highlighted showing its varying degrees of integration in Europe and the U.S., particularly in therapeutic areas like oncology, anti-infectives, and haematology. These areas benefit most from RWE, which predominantly supports safety assessments and, to a lesser extent, efficacy.
- The presentation emphasised the potential of RWE across the entire product lifecycle, including pre-authorization phases. This early involvement with regulators can aid in obtaining designations, scientific advice, and paediatric investigation plans. Despite initial scepticism, the demand for RWE in these stages has proven significant.
- RWE studies are grouped into three main types: representativeness and validity, feasibility for planning studies, and understanding clinical contexts. These studies help regulators ensure that submitted studies are representative and feasible, understand disease epidemiology, and monitor the real-world use of newly approved drugs. Safety and the impact of regulatory actions are also critical areas where RWE is applied.
- Specific examples of RWE utilization were shared from the first 18 months of the Darwin EU initiative. The initiative has primarily focused on safety, study design feasibility, drug utilisation, and disease epidemiology. Highlighting the considerable demand from committees dealing with paediatric and rare diseases, and illustrating the need for multinational studies and federated data networks.

- The operational structure of Darwin EU includes in-house studies, external contractors, and a federated network of data partners. This network allows for generating RWE directly by regulators. A key aspect of the network is the use of a common data model (CDM), which standardises data structures and content across various sources, facilitating faster and more consistent analyses while protecting patient privacy.
- The Darwin EU project, in its third year, aims to conduct numerous studies annually. The network has onboarded diverse data partners, including hospitals, GP practices, and specialised databases like cancer registries and biobanks. The standardisation enabled by the CDM, and standardised analytics have significantly increased study speed and reliability.
- Several recent studies were highlighted, showing a focus on rare diseases, oncology, and paediatric conditions.
- While the federated network has demonstrated its capacity to deliver RWE for regulatory purposes, there is still room for improvement in mapping data, enhancing standardised analytical pipelines, and balancing stakeholder needs with the quest for automation.

Discussion

The discussion highlighted the ongoing challenge with the OMOP project, balancing the need for quick additional data mapping against the comprehensive initial mapping of all data. It was agreed that an iterative process is essential, tailoring data mapping to specific use cases to achieve an optimal balance.

A participant raised a question regarding the role of industry in data mapping, training, and expertise. The speaker clarified that while entities like IQVIA, which owns significant data, are involved, the pharma industry currently cannot use the Darwin network. She expressed hope for future collaboration while maintaining regulatory independence.

A participant enquired about the funding scale and data partner lessons. It was explained that the program is publicly funded, avoiding industry involvement to ensure independence. Initially, data partners needed pre-converted OMOP data but now partners willing to convert data within a reasonable timeframe are considered. Challenges include ensuring data quality and addressing gaps.

The speaker identified significant data gaps, such as the need for more linked primary and secondary data sources and cancer registries. Medication data mapping remains a recurring issue due to its complexity. Additionally, the scalability of data partner resources and infrastructure presents challenges.

A Participant shared insights from other countries like Finland, where centralised collaboration with data partners has facilitated work. They noted that frequently used data partners often become overloaded, causing delays. The need for infrastructure scalability and adequate training for data scientists was emphasised.

NHS SDE OMOP Mapping landscape (Kehinde Adenaiye-NHS, South central and west commission)

[\[Presentation Slides\]](#)

This presentation provides an overview of a survey conducted to assess the OMOP mapping status across the NHS Research Secure Data Environment (SDE) Network. The survey aimed to understand the current position and future direction of OMOP mapping within the SDE.

- The survey, conducted by the Technology and Data Working Group between February and March, gathered information from all 12 SDEs. The survey sought to identify which SDE have undertaken OMOP mapping, the datasets involved, the tools used, and any published mappings. Responses indicated that four SDEs have completed some OMOP mapping, five have not undertaken any, and four are in the process of mapping.
- Key drivers for OMOP mapping included making data accessible for Cohort Discovery (in the Health Data Research Gateway) and meeting researcher requests. Examples of datasets mapped to the OMOP CDM included reporting, radiotherapy, myeloma, maternity, and cancer datasets. Tools supporting the mapping process included dbt, Azure, Databricks, SQL, Python, and Carrot Mapper.
- Regarding publication, two SDEs had already published their OMOP mappings, with four more planning to do so. Barriers to OMOP mapping included issues with vocabulary mapping, time and resource constraints, understanding source and target structures, limited publicly available mappings, and financial implications.
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Discussion

There was a strong consensus on the need for transparency and collaboration to improve the overall quality and accessibility of data. One participant emphasized the importance of making survey results and data mappings publicly available, noting that some have already been shared on the HDR UK Innovation Gateway under the Tools section. This allows different SDEs to share their mappings, which can help others struggling with similar issues and foster a collaborative problem-solving environment.

There was also a discussion about the resources available within different SDEs to undertake OMOP mapping. It was noted that the level of resources and the time required for mapping vary among SDEs, depending on their maturity and the complexity of their data sets. Some SDEs are conducting the mappings in-house, while others are outsourcing to specialist firms. A participant pointed out that it is inefficient for multiple entities to map the same national data sets independently. Instead, there should be a coordinated effort to standardise these mappings at a national level and redistribute them to avoid redundancy and save resources.

Another critical point raised was the role of commercial organizations in the real-world evidence network. The discussion highlighted the potential benefits of involving commercial partners in data mapping, quality certification, and facilitating research studies. A participant recognised the necessity of setting clear boundaries and governance to ensure that collaborations with commercial entities are beneficial and aligned with public interests.

Attending Organisations

Answer Digital

1. Arcturis: Advancing Insight Using Real World Data
2. Aridhia DRE Trusted Data Sharing Network
3. Astra Zeneca
4. Barts Health NHS Trust
5. Barts Life Sciences

6. Barth Spa University
7. Canon Medical Research Europe
8. Clinical Architecture Healthcare Data Quality
9. Clinical Architecture Healthcare Data Quality and Interoperability
10. European Medicine Agency
11. FIT FILE
12. Genomics England
13. Great Ormond Street Hospital Trust
14. Guys and St Thomas NHS Foundation Trust
15. Health Innovation East
16. Healthcare Consulting: Carnall Farrar
17. Holmusk
18. Health Data Research UK
19. Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust
20. Imperial College London
21. IQVIA
22. Kings College Hospital
23. Leeds Teaching Hospital
24. Maidstone and Tunbridge Wells NHS Trust
25. Medicine and Healthcare Products Regulatory Agency
26. MRC Biostatistics Unit-UKRI
27. MyWellSpan
28. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
29. NHS England
30. NHS Norfolk and Waveney Integrated Care Board
31. NHS Norfolk and Waveney Integrated Care Board (ICB)
32. Nottingham University Hospital
33. Office of National Statistics
34. Optimum Patient Care
35. Our Future Health
36. Oxford Health NHS Foundation Trust
37. Oxford University
38. Oxford University Hospitals
39. Public Health Scotland
40. Research Data Scotland
41. Sheffield Hallam University
42. Sonnetix
43. Software Architect at University of Oxford
44. Swansea University
45. University College London
46. University Hospitals Birmingham NHS Foundation Trust
47. University Hospital Southampton
48. University Hospital Southampton NHS Foundation Trust
49. University of Aberdeen
50. University of Bristol
51. University of Cambridge-MRC Biostatistics Unit
52. University of Leeds
53. University of Leeds Teaching Hospital

54. University of Limerick
55. University of Nottingham
56. WellSpan Health
57. Wrightington, Wigan and Leigh NHS Foundation Trust